

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable D2.2.1b

Concept for the organisation of a distributed user support network (USN) in NFDI4Earth

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Executive summary

This concept describes the organisation and implementation of the NFDI4Earth distributed user support network (USN), steps of implementation and participation, quality measures as well as the embedment in other support structures. The annex contains the description of the initial coverage, the support categories and the planned actions.

Abbreviations

ESS - Earth System Sciences

LHB - Living Handbook

OTRS - Open Ticket Request System

RDM - Research Data Management

SOP - Standard Operating Procedures

USN - User Support Network

OS4A - OneStop4All

TUDD - Technical University of Dresden

GEOMAR- Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research, Kiel

LRZ - Leibniz Supercomputing Centre

GFZ - Helmholtz Centre Potsdam

UNIHH - Universität hamburg

FUB - Freie Universität Berlin

DKRZ - Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum

KIT - Karlsruhe Institute of Technology

Contents

1. Introduction	1
2. Implementation	1
2.1. Process of Operation	1
2.2. Participation principles for new USN members	3
2.3. Improvement Process	3
2.4. Embedment in NFDI4Earth support structures	5
A. Initial Partners	6
B. Initial Support categories	6
B.1. Repositories (Category #1)	6
B.2. Tools/Software (Category #3)	7
B.3. Services (Category #4)	7
B.4. Data and analysis (Category #5)	7
B.5. General information and metadata (Category #2)	7
B.6. Future Topics	8
C. Actions, Deliverables and Milestones	8

1. Introduction

The NFDI4Earth consortium covers the complete scope of Earth System Sciences and a considerable diversity of research data, data infrastructures, and data management methods. One goal of NFDI4Earth is to create a federated data infrastructure based on the existing applications and repositories as well as to enable researchers to handle their data according to the FAIR principles. Therefore, NFDI4Earth provides various interconnected measures to support the different users, e.g., researchers, research data managers, and infrastructure providers. The general idea is to provide an information portal, the OneStop4All (OS4A), giving access to all NFDI4Earth resources. In case, the provided information is not sufficient to answer a given question, users can reach out to support experts via a ticketing system. Provided solutions will additionally be documented in the Living Handbook (LHB) for further re-use and enhancement of the OS4A. Considering the complexity of ESS and its diverse community, it is almost impossible to cover this with one single group of RDM support experts. Instead, a network of specialized support groups is envisioned, that operates as a distributed user support network (USN), ideally covering the complete range of the NFDI4Earth community.

RDM support expertise in the different domains and subdisciplines of ESS has already been established in at least some NFDI4Earth member institutions. The USN aims at connecting these existing institutional RDM support groups to a larger system, open for each given and upcoming RDM support group, initially starting with eight member institutions of NFDI4Earth. This initial network has analysed the given support expertise and coverage of disciplines, as well as RDM methods, tools and infrastructures. Identified support gaps will be closed by including additional USN members and creating new support content. The benefit for new members is a greater visibility of their support expertise.

The present concept describes the organisation and implementation of the USN, quality measures as well as the initial coverage.

2. Implementation

After initial steps have been taken, the implementation process of the USN begins and comprises the process of operating the USN, including a lightweight cooperation agreement, and participation principles for all USN members.

2.1. Process of Operation

The process of operation describes the way, support requests are handled by USN members and the documentation of solutions. It also includes the availability of the USN.

2.1.1. Flow of requests

In general, the USN is organised like any other user support. The main difference is the distribution of USN members over several institutions. Hence, there is no head of operation, but only coordination for supporters in charge. The command chain for this organisational body will be regulated in the USN cooperation agreement (see below). The USN is operating on a ticket system (OTRS provided by TU Dresden), which allows the typical supporter–user interaction. Details are described in the *USN OTRS concept (D2.2.2)*. Therefore, the first contact for users into the USN is a request via ticket. This ticket will be interpreted by the first (1st) level support and a) directly be answered to the user or b) assigned to a specific part of the second (2nd) level, according to the predefined support categories (and established queues in the ticket system, respectively). The 2nd level consists of the member groups of the USN, covering the different support domains. If the 2nd level support is involved, they will contact the user directly.

2.1.2. Documentation

Documentation is twofold in the USN. First of all, USN design and processes will be documented as well as support expertise of the members and support categories, as indicated already in Appendix A (Initial Partners) and Appendix B (Initial Support categories).

Secondly, solutions to requests shall be documented. As a working version, this may be attached to the request documentation. To make the solution available in the NFDI4Earth support ecosystem for the whole NFDI4Earth community, they will be documented as solution articles for the Living Handbook. Authors are USN members in charge and documentation will make use of provided living handbook templates (see *LHB*). A detailed documentation concept will be delivered as D2.2.3.

2.1.3. Work schedules

Since the USN consists of already specialized 2nd level support groups, only the 1st level has to be organized by these groups. Ideally, each member group takes over the 1st level support service for a certain period, e.g. altering each month.

Work schedules for USN members are developed by the measure lead together with the contact persons of the group members. There are no experiences yet concerning expected support workload within the USN and USN member groups are expected to have their own (institutional) support routines anyway. Hence, the work schedules are reduced to a) ensuring the availability of support expertise on domains agreed upon, and b) availability of experts within a given time frame.

2.1.4. Cooperation agreement

A lightweight USN cooperation agreement (USN CA) regulates the rights and obligations of each USN member group. This is even more important, since the USN will depend on the engagement and openness of existing institutional support groups. Hence, one central component of the USN CA will be an agreement on the commitment of each USN member group to support NFDI4Earth community members regardless of their institutional affiliation.

A first draft of the USN CA will be provided to be approved by the legal departments of each USN member institution. After approval, the USN CA will supplement the NFDI4Earth consortium agreement.

2.2. Participation principles for new USN members

The initial USN size of eight members will not be sufficient to cover the complete range of ESS domains and disciplines. Hence, new members are welcome at any time. There are only a few principles new members have to accept to participate. New members

1. sign the USN cooperation agreement
2. define domains and disciplines, they are willing and able to support
3. define RDM methods, tools and infrastructures, they are willing and able to support
4. accept the operational processes including timeframes
5. accept the documentation rules
6. agree to actively participate in the network and the overall improvement cycle

2.3. Improvement Process

The USN will develop and establish an improvement process to ensure a continuous monitoring of the support quality and the underlying processes. This improvement process will be implemented as a cycle including an annual supporter meeting and report.

Improvements are based on collected statistics and monitoring of request processing as well as on regular user surveys.

Additionally, an annual improvement workshop will define upcoming adjustments, possible re-design and further development steps for the support network.

The overall concept for the annual improvement cycle will be developed in D2.2.4.

2.3.1. Collecting request handling information

For quality assurance and improvement of support service, a set of metadata shall be assigned to each request. Assignment can be achieved in different ways:

1. The USN entry point at the Onestop4All allows users to assign some metadata to their request.
2. Supporters will add metadata during request handling.
3. Metadata will also be assigned automatically during request processing by the ticket system.

The set of metadata assigned by human may include some personal information of the user, like email address, affiliation, professional background (like role and discipline), the assigned support category provided by the USN entry point, and some specialized information depending on the selected category (e.g. specific repository). Information by supporters may be the categorisation of solutions provided to a specific request.

Having the ticket system as a tool of direct contact to users, it can be used to create automated metadata, i.e. date and time of request and its processing steps, number of contacts per request, count of (successfully) closed tickets, and so on. The range of automated information depends on the opportunities of the implemented ticketing system.

Which metadata set and additional information will be provided has to be specified in the deliverable D2.2.4.

2.3.2. User feedback

As described above, the USN is embedded in a set of support measures and is strongly intertwined with the OneStop4All, Knowledge Hub and the Living Handbook. Since the provided knowledge in these measures is expected to increase also by USN-provided request solutions, the USN is interested in how users use the USN, if solutions to the request are provided and how the user requests develop over time, e.g. if requests are getting more specific and more precise with growing content in the Knowledge HUB and Living Handbook.

The USN will develop a questionnaire and will conduct (together with other measures or alone) an annual survey on USN users. This survey might be included in user surveys from other measures.

To get feedback from potential USN users, we will contact existing networks, e.g., postgraduate schools and postdoc networks as well as every cohort of NFDI4Earth pilot projects.

As research data handling can be very special in different scientific communities, the USN will also evaluate if an open community support system (like [Stack Overflow](#)) will be of value next to the institutional RDM support of the USN team.

Specification of these measures is part of deliverable D2.2.4.

2.4. Embedment in NFDI4Earth support structures

The USN is embedded into the support ecosystem of NFDI4Earth. A more detailed description can be found in the OnePager (see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7583595>).

2.4.1. OneStop4All

The user of NFDI4Earth is expected to visit the OneStop4All to access the information, services and material which builds the national research data infrastructure for earth system science. In the portal, users are expected to be guided to the required information and find the answers for their demands on their own. Only a part of the users is expected to require individual consulting. These are then forwarded to the support with direct user contact via the OTRS.

2.4.2. OTRS

The ticketing system, technically provided by the TA4, will be customised by the USN. The OTRS concept (see D2.2.2) defines the response time, queues and agent roles and their internal communication to provide a well-defined support in the, above mentioned, support categories. This direct contact of the USN agents to the users will give insight into the needs of the user and will be used to improve the information given in the OneStop4All and the Living Handbook.

2.4.3. Living Handbook (LHB)

The Living Handbook will be used by the USN as its long-term memory - adding and retrieving information to make the user support a community effort with constant quality improvement. The USN will send a representative to the editorial board of the LHB, to be part of the content development and selection, according to the needs and experiences gained from the direct contact to the user. For 2023 the USN group named Christopher Purr (UNIHH) to be member of the board. This decision needs to be renewed every year, and will be part of the annual workshop agenda, where also new partners are expected to be present and can be included.

2.4.4. Connection to pilots

The NFDI4Earth pilots are seen as early users of the common NFDI4Earth infrastructure and this includes the user support. A short questionnaire will be created to get feedback from this

group on where they got sufficient support so far and in which fields they were missing support. They will hopefully also be the first users of the OTRS and can help us to test our concept on real use cases.

Appendix

A. Initial Partners

The USN has eight initial partners (GEOMAR, LRZ, GFZ, TUDD, UNIH, FUB, DKRZ, KIT), constituting the distributed user support network. Four of these partners have positions via NFDI4Earth to develop and coordinate the main USN components. Each initial partner has established an institutional support group already or has a support expertise for a data domain, RDM methods or infrastructures. A first distribution of support expertise has been developed on the initial USN workshop in September 2022 (see additional table **USN-Support-Mapping.xlsx**). In addition, partners can draw on general institutional RDM support desks (i.e., the universities), located in or between data centres and libraries.

The initial group already covers or has a strong connection to domain communities, like the marine, atmospheric, terrestrial, hydrological or seismic community. It is intended, to widen the scope by integrating new network partners.

B. Initial Support categories

In order to be able to process support requests as quickly and satisfactorily as possible, it makes sense to categorize them so that the various competencies in the User Support Network (USN) can be used as effectively as possible. At the beginning, the following five categories will be developed. Further three categories will be established step by step, since for these further developments of the structure of the NFDI4Earth are necessary. In order to act as close to the user as possible, the categories and their definition are taken from the "user stories" and are thus closely oriented to the needs of the user.

B.1. Repositories (Category #1)

A variety of data repositories exist for the different scientific topics, which differ in their functionality. In order to provide the user with guidance in the selection of a suitable repository for data publication and in its use, depending on the type of data, consulting support is provided here. Users are also advised on data archiving with regard to, among other things,

storage duration and geographical distribution. In terms of general storage solutions, a variety of data lifecycle topics are covered, ranging from access via APIs to data curation and publishing.

B.2. Tools/Software (Category #3)

There are many different RDM software solutions available. The aim is to help users to find an adequate solution taking into account the respective scientific domain and requirements. The selection is based on the experience of previous users, which is gathered either by the pilots or by expertise available in the USN. Support will also be provided for the usage, especially if this is not straightforward, e.g., if APIs need to be used.

B.3. Services (Category #4)

The support category „Services“ covers users that would like to know where they can get computing and data resources, i.e. basic infrastructure. All other requests are to be considered requests on „Repositories“ (#1), „Data and analysis“ (#5), or „General information and metadata“ (#2). Thus, it is merely a „catch category“ for issues we do not actually support, but where support requests are forwarded to infrastructure providers. As subcategories, it covers the virtual research environment, computational resources, and disc space (close to computational/cloud resources, standalone, or as exchange platform).

B.4. Data and analysis (Category #5)

This category clusters support requests that involve questions about datasets and their analysis or reusing them. The whole range of meta-analysis is covered ranging from retrieval via appropriate keywords or related publications, via access, to analysis by means of, e.g., visualization or evaluation using appropriate metrics.

B.5. General information and metadata (Category #2)

More in-depth advice on general information about the FAIR principles and their application can be provided in this category „General information and metadata“, if requests cannot be handled by established services of the NFDI4Earth (e.g.: Knowledge Hub or Living Handbook). NFDI4Earth specific support is provided to facilitate the use of e.g., the OneStop4All or the EduTrain or to assist with the inclusion of new services into the NFDI4Earth. Support is also provided for specific topics such as metadata in repositories, metadata standards, ontologies, and data management plans.

B.6. Future Topics

Once the support structures are established, the following categories will be gradually added to the support. The support category **“Participation in NFDI4Earth” (Category #6)** covers requests regarding contact, participation or promotion of the NFDI4Earth. Another category is **“Community and networking” (Category #7)**, which covers requests about organizations, the Community Forum, and networking. Finally, requests for **“Educational materials” (Category #8)** are handled where users can get help with curriculums regarding type, subject and difficulty level.

C. Actions, Deliverables and Milestones

For the USN, the NFDI4Earth proposal (see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5718943>) described four actions:

Action 1: Establish the User Support Network (USN)

Develop and implement a concept for the integration of existing RDM support structures into NFDI4Earth and operate the USN, substantiated with the implementation of a lightweight USN cooperation agreement between USN members, defining the rules and roles of each member. The USN cooperation agreement will supplement the NFDI4Earth consortium agreement (M4.1). The USN establishment process will compile partners and expertise and will define rules of participation as well as define and implement USN internal standard operating procedures (SOPs) for USN members. Annual workshops and interested RDM support groups will bring together people and initiate and frame the continuous improvement process of the USN. The initial workshop will be held in Q2/2022, in order to make the USN ready to support the first NFDI4Earth pilots starting.

Action 2: Customise the Ticketing System (together with M2.1)

The ticketing system, technically provided by the TA4, will be customised by the USN. Action 2 will define terms of use and the rules and roles (responsibilities) among the partners for the basic internal support platform. Additionally, Action 2 defines (together with M2.1) and implements support categories for automated provision (distribution) of support requests and content tagging for automated publication of e.g. a FAQ list at OneStop4All (M2.1).

Action 3: Provide content for the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub

The USN will provide content for the Knowledge Hub, in particular for the NFDI4Earth Living Handbooks, edited by M.3.3, produced according to previously defined documentation standards for USN supporters. Additionally, user-relevant gaps in the Knowledge Hub

documentation will be identified, collected and communicated to the corresponding measures in TA3.

Action 4: Implement a USN quality improvement cycle

The quality improvement cycle will ensure continuous facilitation of NFDI4Earth user support, based on collected USN statistics and request monitoring as well as on the regular user surveys implemented by this action. The aim is the development and establishment of an annual quality improvement cycle, including a supporter meeting (see action 1) and an annual report.